

LANGUAGE MEMORY IN MOVLUD SÜLEYMANLI'S NOVEL "KOCH"

Ibrahimova U.*PhD student of Baku State University*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15397807>**Abstract**

Language, which serves as a means of communication between people, is the result of historical evolution. Language contains the memory of history, and as it brings us to the present, it also carries a trace of that history to the future. In modern languages, historical examples are mainly preserved in dialect words and obsolete vocabulary. Poets and writers who create serious literary examples use language like a painter's brush in their works. Just as an artist takes various paints and creates wonderful paintings with his brush, word artists add richness to the language of a work of art by selecting words from various layers of the language's vocabulary. A true writer is a writer who can skillfully bring not only general words, but also words from special lexical groups into his artistic language. Azerbaijani writer Movlud Suleymanli managed to cope with this adequately in his novel "Koch" ("Migration"). The article involves the study of dialectisms and obsolete words that the writer brought into the artistic language of the novel, filtered from the people's memory.

Keywords: literary language, obsolete words, historicisms, archaisms, dialectisms, artistic language, Movlud Suleymanli

Introduction

Throughout human history, language has always been a means of communication. It has been possible for people to communicate with other people living in the same time and place, or with people living in another time and place, through language. Oral literature, which is passed down from language to language and spans centuries, and written literature, which connects centuries, make communication possible between people who do not live in the same time or place.

Language develops as a result of evolution. Sometimes new words enter the lexicon of the language, sometimes functional words fall out of use. Thus, changes occur in the lexical layer. Written literature is an important source from which we can observe these changes. We can see the lexical differences of the literary language more clearly by comparing examples of written literature. The Azerbaijani language, which belongs to the Oghuz group of the Turkic language family, is a language with an ancient history. In the modern Azerbaijani language, traces of history are preserved in the folk colloquial language, which is the embodiment of folk memory.

The article studies the elements of the vernacular language used in the novel "Koch" by the representative of the famous 60s generation of Azerbaijani literature, People's Writer Movlud Suleymanli. The writer is a prominent representative of Azerbaijani literature. Every line and every sentence he wrote carries deep and meaningful traces of history. The author has given a treasure to both Azerbaijani literature and the modern Azerbaijani language with stories, narratives and novels that are rich in language and content.

Main body

Movlud Suleymanli was born on March 18, 1943, in the village of Jujakand in Western Azerbaijan (now Armenia). Movlud, who lost his father in World War II, was raised by his mother. In 1962, he entered the Philology Faculty of Azerbaijan State University and graduated from this university in 1967.

He worked for a while as an editor, screenwriter, and manager in various television, radio, and magazines. The main factors characterizing the literary activity of M. Suleymanli, who began his creative work with poems, are that the history, ethnography, moral and ethical values, and patriotic feelings of the people he belongs to are in the foreground in his works. The writer, who learned and revived the millennial culture and mythology of the Oghuz Turks from scratch and used it as the cornerstone of his art, published stories one after another in the second half of the 1970s. Starting from the 1980s, the writer turned more to the novel genre.

The writer's novels "Koch", "Ceviz kurdu", "Ses" are considered an important step in the development of modern Azerbaijani novel studies. "Koch", the first of three complementary novels by Mevlud Suleymanli, is written in the mythological way of thinking of the ancient Turks living in the geography of Azerbaijan. In this work, the author, using the power of literary language, writes about the ancient Turkic history of the Caucasus geography.

The ancient lexical layer of the Azerbaijani language has been used by the people who speak this language for centuries. In general, the words that make up the vocabulary of the language form the active and passive lexicon of the language: "The passive part of the dictionary includes words that have lost their ability to be used, remained in old literature, dictionaries and are familiar to very few people, and at the same time, words that have recently entered the language due to certain relationships and have not yet found a solid foundation for themselves." [1, p. 65] It is known that the vocabulary of the Azerbaijani language does not consist only of words used in the literary language, but also in folk dialects, obsolete words, which are an important part of the vocabulary of the language used in literary works.

As we have already mentioned, in his novel "Koch", Mevlud Suleymanli wrote down the history of the ancient Turkic people, which is preserved in the memory of the people. This history is preserved in the

search for a homeland of the nomadic people, in the livestock breeding life of the people who have a homeland, and in every stone and rock of the village..

In their works on different topics, writers use special word groups within their own style to convey real-life scenes – the objects and events described - to the reader in a unique way, both in their narrative and in the speech of the characters. Movlud Suleymanli also formed his own artistic style in his own way, without tiring the reader, by using each word in its place. The reader who reads his works does not get tired in any way, the words and idioms of the author are not alien to the reader, but are from the folk language. It is worth noting that in the stories of the writer, the description and singing of the general landscape of the village, descriptions of nature, and the village population are distinguished by their characteristic features in terms of artistry and originality. Movlud Suleymanli, who knew village life perfectly and wrote a number of works on this subject, used new idioms in the description of the Azerbaijani village, through expressions that filtered from the people's memory.

The writer has included dialect words in his literary language. The words in the vocabulary of dialects and dialects are the product of many centuries. While over time, a number of words have disappeared from the vocabulary of the literary language, dialects and dialects retain and preserve those words for a long time. In this regard, the dialects and dialects of the Azerbaijani language have a rich vocabulary. Movlud Suleymanli skillfully used this rich treasure in his work and created a literary masterpiece.

In a literary work, dialectisms are presented either in the author's narration or in the speech of the characters: "Lexical and ethnographic types of dialectisms can be found in the author's speech." [4, p. 236] In the literary language of Movlud Suleymanli, examples of dialects belonging to the western group of the Azerbaijani language are used: *arxac* (*arkhaj*), *xalxal* (*khalkhal*), *tənə* (*tene*), *şax* (*shakh*), *genəşik* (*genashik*). We can also associate this with the fact that the author was born and grew up in Western Azerbaijan.

İlxılarınız hürkəcək hələ, sürüləriniz arxacdan qopacaq, itləriniz hələ təzə yurda hürəcək. [Your sheep will still be afraid, your flocks will break away from the herd, your dogs will still bark in their new home.]

"Arkhaj" in the Bashkechid and Borchali dialects is a specific place created in the open air by herds and flocks during the warm seasons of the year.

İki təpənin arsına çıxdılar. Köhnə yurd yerləri vardı, daş xalxallar vardı. [They went up between two hills. There were old settlements, stone huts.]

In most Western dialects of Azerbaijan, the word "khalkhal" refers to a fenced area for keeping livestock in the open air. Here, it is also used to mean an area surrounded by stones for keeping animals near old country places.

İzn ver, düşək, qoxuçiçəyi yığaq, Dədə. Qulağımızın tənəsi qoxulanmır. [Let us go down and gather the fragrant flowers, Grandfather. Our ears are not fragrant.]

The word "tane" is used in the Shamkir and Shusha dialects to mean the soft part of the ear or an earring.

Oğlan evi oğlan şaxı bəzədi, qız evi qız şaxı bəzədi. [The boy's house decorated the boy's shakh, the girl's house decorated the girl's shakh.]

In the Borchali, Dashkesan, and Tartar dialects, a "shakh" is a piece of branch decorated with sweets and fruits, brought as a gift by close friends to the bride or groom during wedding ceremonies. This custom is still preserved in regions today.

Qarakəllələrin genəşik yeri olmuşdu. [There was a wide space for the Karakelles.]

This example of dialectism is not found in dictionaries. However, it is known that the word [geşshikh'li] is used in the Tovuz dialect in the sense of "advisory". The short form of the word used by the author also conveys the same meaning.

As history progressed and the Turkic lineage, the Turkic people, the ancient people of these lands were deported from Western Azerbaijan, which is now considered the territory of the Armenian state [7]. And thus, the history of the Oghuz people living in the territory of Western Azerbaijan slowly began to be forgotten. In this work, the author wrote about the history of the most ancient Turks in the Caucasus region, then the Turkic tribes that migrated from Central Asia, the ancient Caucasian peoples who lived here together, and the European peoples who were resettled to this territory in the 20th century, and expressed his literary protest against the forgetting of this history without offending anyone or harming the political interests of any state. During the years of Soviet rule, a total of 8 German colonies were established in various territories of Azerbaijan [8]. Suleymanli also touched upon this fact in his work.

We said that the work "Koch" reflects the history of a people, perhaps of humanity. This work uses not only examples from the Western group of dialects, but also examples from the ancient Turkic language in general – obsolete words: *alaçiq* (*alachig*), *arı* (*ari*), *bəylik* (*bakhlik*), *xanlıq* (*khanlig*), *oba*, *qayım* (*qayim*). In Azerbaijani linguistics, obsolete words are grouped into two types: archaisms and historicisms. "Archaisms are words that are rarely used in the modern language and are related to old customs and lifestyles." [3, p. 237] "Archaic words have various stylistic nuances and can be used in different styles and in different situations, depending on the stylistic purpose." [5, p. 124]

Dəyə çubuqlarını qurdular, alaçıqları hazır elədilər... [They set up their poles, prepared their tents...]

"Alachig" is a nomadic dwelling, tent, common among ancient Turkic and Mongolian peoples, made of sticks and covered with felt. These tents are usually made of sticks buried in the ground in a circular shape, the upper ends of which are connected in a dome shape, and felt is placed on top. The bottom is surrounded by a woven net made of sticks and reeds. The entrance to the alachiq does not have a door, but is covered with felt or a rug. In some areas, it is still used by people engaged in nomadic cattle breeding today.

Suların durusu, çörəyin arısı ortaya gəldi. [The purity of the waters and the purity of the bread appeared.]

“Although archaic words become obsolete, they do not completely disappear from the language, only their range of use is limited.” [2, p. 315] In modern Azerbaijani, the word “ari” means a winged insect that produces honey. However, in historical texts, “ari” is used in the meanings of clean, pure, clear, bright and pure. In Turkic languages, the words “artlamak” – to clean, “arınmaq” – to purify, which are derived from this root, are also used. In this example, Mevlud Suleymanlı used the word “ari” with its ancient meaning of clean, pure.

Bir adam lazım idi bayraq kimi, qabağa çıxaydı, – “Haydi, igidlər, – deyəydi, – xan tutaq, xanlıq alağ, bəy vuraq, bəylik yıxaq”. [A man was needed, like a flag, to step forward, saying, “Come on, brave men,” he would say, “let's seize a khan, take a khanate, defeat a bey, and overthrow a bey.”]

“Beylik” was a functional word in the culture of the ancient Turks and meant something that belonged to a bey, the lord. “Beylik” refers to a piece of land under the control of a bey or the way these lands were governed. Beyliks could usually be independent or subordinate to some great empire. “Khanlig” also means a country, territory, or territory belonging to a khan and under the control of a khan. The difference between a khanlig and a beylik was that khanligs were feudal states that existed in the Middle Ages mainly in areas inhabited by Turkic peoples. Both words are currently used in modern Azerbaijani language, along with their historical meanings, more often in the sense of belonging to a bey or worthy of khans and beys. In the text, the writer presented the words in their historical meaning.

Günəş dağları, obaları, ormanları, sürüləri, ilxıları təmizləyə-təmizləyə, suları aydınlada-aydınlada, yuxuları çinlədə-çinlədə qalxırdı. [The sun rose, cleansing the mountains, villages, forests, herds, and flocks, illuminating the waters, and dispelling dreams.]

The ancient Turks established small settlements consisting of a few houses in the areas they settled. Such villages or settlements were called “oba”. Among the nomadic Turks who were engaged in animal husbandry, “oba” also meant a migratory place, a nomadic camp, consisting of several huts or tents, where the nomads temporarily resided.

Qurulu dövlətmə yıxıb gəlirdi bu köçün adamları, yoxsa dövlətmə qurmağa gəlirdi ki, belə azman, belə göylərdən, yerlərdən qorxmaz, belə bir, belə qayım, belə bütöv... [Were these people of this migration coming to destroy an established state, or were they coming to build a state that was so vast, so fearless of the heavens and the earth, so one, so strong, so complete...]

“Qayım” in ancient Turkic meant high, solid. Nowadays, it has various meanings such as solid, firm, heavy, consistent; stingy, stingy, and solid. Likewise, in Western dialects, it denotes a verb in the sense of solid.

The author conveys the historical nuance to the reader by using such historical words that are not used in the active lexicon of the modern Azerbaijani

language. The author symbolically describes how the people who migrated on horseback were born on horseback, grew up on horseback, got married on horseback, grew old and passed away on horseback. In ancient Turkic culture, the horse was considered sacred. The horse is the companion of the Turk. In the literary language of Mevlud Suleymanlı, it is possible to read dozens of such examples related to the Turkish way of life.

Conclusion

The history of the Turks is rich. Suleymanlı touched on this topic not only in his work “Koch”, but in almost all his works. Writing about such topics and creating works that would stir the memory of the people during the years of Soviet rule in Azerbaijan required great courage in itself. Mevlud Suleymanlı was a writer who was able to do this. The main factor that distinguishes and characterizes his creativity is that it is possible to benefit from the history, ethnography, moral and ethical values, and folklore sources of the people he belongs to in his works. His works are dominated by the grandeur, figurative language, and patriotic spirit that come from ancient Turkish epic thinking. What has been said does not only determine the writer's form and language, but rather determines their spirit and warmth.

In conclusion, we can note that the author's work “Koch” that means migration explains the migration of humanity to the reader through the example of a people. The history of all the peoples who have been looking for a homeland for thousands of years, who have not been able to settle in the land they have sought, who have despised their neighbors, who have tried to dominate other lands, who have had a homeland but have not been able to own it, is reflected in this work. The language of the work is very rich. In order to express historical images, space and time, the author has used elements of folk speech, especially dialect and obsolete words as a means. The use of these examples in the work does not tire the reader, but on the contrary helps him understand the content of the work.

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